

Graphical Abstract

A multiscale discrete element thermomechanical modelling approach of microcracking generated at high temperature by anisotropic thermal expansion in an elastic brittle polycrystalline ceramic material

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Highlights

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- Purpose of the Study : Modeling microcracking in brittle ceramic materials under high-temperature conditions using a novel multiscale discrete element method.
- Key Findings : Quantitative predictions of macroscopic thermo-mechanical properties that align well with experimental observations.
- Novel Contribution : Development and validation of a new multiscale DEM approach accounting for anisotropic thermal expansion, thermomechanical coupling, and crack propagation under periodic boundary conditions.
- Applications : Enhancing understanding of material toughening and improving thermal shock resistance in industrial ceramics.

A multiscale discrete element thermomechanical modelling approach of microcracking generated at high temperature by anisotropic thermal expansion in an elastic brittle polycrystalline ceramic material

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Abstract

Aluminum titanate is widely used in various industries due to its superior intrinsic properties for thermal shock applications. At the microstructural scale, this material is characterized by its original grain crystallinity, leading to anisotropic thermal expansion behavior at the crystallographic grain level. Consequently, aluminum titanate undergoes spontaneous microcracking at high temperatures during operational conditions due to mismatches in the Coefficient of Thermal Expansion (CTE) between grains. These microcracks within the refractory microstructure result in quasi-brittle, non-linear mechanical behavior under tensile loading. Experimental findings suggest that the non-linear macroscopic response signifies material toughening, enhancing fracture toughness and, consequently, improving its thermal shock resistance. To better understand these phenomena, this study presents a simplified polycrystalline microstructure model using the Discrete Element Method (DEM), with aluminum titanate as the reference material. The research focuses on predicting the role of grain-level thermal anisotropy in microcrack nucleation and propagation, critical for thermal shock sustainability. A novel DEM approach, based on the bonded particle element method, is proposed. This approach quantitatively accounts for anisotropic CTE, thermomechanical coupling, crack nucleation, propagation and closure under Periodic Boundary Conditions (PBC), enabling multiscale analysis. The results obtained align quantitatively with experimental macroscopic observations, including the evolution of CTE and Young's modulus with temperature.

Keywords: Thermomechanics, Discrete Element Method (DEM), Refractory material, Microstructure, Microcracks, Anisotropy

1. Introduction

Refractory materials, such as aluminum titanate, are extensively utilized in the steel and glass-making industries due to their exceptional intrinsic properties, particularly for thermal shock applications. At the microstructural level, these materials are characterized by the crystallinity of their grains [1]. For instance, aluminum titanate is a polycrystalline material that features orthorhombic crystals, a non-cubic crystal structure observable at the microstructural scale (see Figure 1). As a result, materials like aluminum titanate exhibit anisotropic thermal expansion, where expansion varies

along different crystallographic directions. This behavior is intrinsic to the material's microscopic structure. Furthermore, under high-temperature operational conditions, these materials tend to develop spontaneous microcracking due to thermal stresses [1, 2, 3].

Previous studies have emphasized that multiple mechanisms contribute to microcracking in refractory materials, including mismatches in the Coefficient of Thermal Expansion (CTE) between phases, aggregate size, and grain crystallinity [1, 3, 4]. Additionally, the presence of microcracks within the refractory microstructure results in a non-linear mechanical macroscopic response [2, 3, 5, 6]. Experimental evidence indicates that this non-linear macroscopic behavior signifies material toughening, enhancing its resilience [2,

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Nomenclature

α	Coefficient of thermal expansion	S	Surface
$\langle q \rangle$	Apparent (macroscopic) quantity q	T	Temperature
$\overline{\overline{\sigma}}$	Cauchy stress tensor	BEM	Boundary Element Method
$\overline{\overline{\varepsilon}}$	Cauchy strain tensor	BPEM	Bonded Particle Element Method
δL	Incremental elongation	CTE	Coefficient of Thermal Expansion
ν	Poisson's ratio	CZM	Cohesive Zone Modeling
σ_{\max}	Failure strength in tension	DE	Discrete Element
$\vec{\Sigma}$	Stress vector	DEM	Discrete Element Method
$\vec{a}, \vec{b}, \vec{c}$	Crystallographic directions	DLSM	Distinct Lattice Spring Model
\vec{f}	Force	FEM	Finite Element Method
E	Young's modulus	PBC	Periodic Boundary Condition
L	Periodic cell length	PFM	Phase Field Modeling

Figure 1: Micrography of Aluminium Titanate material [3]

3, 5, 6]. Specifically, materials with microcracks at the microstructural scale demonstrate greater thermal shock resistance compared to those without microcracks [2, 3]. This phenomenon is illustrated by the macroscopic stress-strain response of aluminum titanate under two distinct microstructural conditions (with and without microcracks), as shown in Figure 2.

The betterment in the material's fracture toughness contributes to the improvement of their thermal shock resistance [7, 8]. In order to prepare such a complex refractory microstructure, the compact sample obtained by the powder compaction process is subjected to a sintering thermal treatment (firing a sample at high ther-

Figure 2: Tensile cycling tests on two Aluminium Titanate [2]

mal cycles, which includes heating, dwell and cooling stages) [3, 9]. The thermal treatment begins at room temperature, and once the high temperature is reached, "the sample is maintained at the high temperature (between 1000°C and 1600°C) for 6 hours to 12 hours" (dwell) and then cooled back to room tempera-

ture [6, 9]. Therefore, the microcracked refractory microstructure is the end result of this thermal treatment process [1, 2, 3, 5, 6].

Simulations of such cracking phenomena, including microcracking, branching, or fragmentation, that occur in brittle or quasi-brittle media, have become a topic of interest in the research field to reduce experimental costs and to develop and test new microstructure designs [10, 11].

One of the approaches was an analytical-based model related to micromechanics-based homogenization techniques, such as the Mori–Tanaka [12] and Eshelby [13] models. Moreover, Bruno et al. [10] proposed an Eshelby-based micromechanical homogenized model to predict internal stresses due to cooling (from 470°C to –170°C) across a cordierite polycrystalline porous microstructure. In this study, the cordierite crystals exhibited anisotropic thermal expansion, which led to microcracking. The authors proposed a model where the input properties included the apparent Young’s modulus, Coefficient of Thermal Expansion (CTE), Poisson’s ratio and the Hill’s tensor (which reflects the shape factor of the pores) [10]. These data were used in deducing the interface strength of the grains, stresses and the crack density promoted across the microstructure. Notably, the authors were able to predict the stresses by utilizing information about the crack density in the microstructure. This enabled them to quantitatively predict the stresses accumulated during the cooling process across the grains in the microstructure [10]. Additionally, the model explained the microcracking saturation effect observed after reaching specific temperature ranges during the cooling process.

However, the authors were unable to directly predict stresses that led to microcrack initiation from a material science perspective without prior knowledge of the crack density. Moreover, the model was not recommended for materials like aluminum titanate, which exhibit very strong anisotropic thermal expansion [10]. Furthermore, other researchers adopted the Finite Element Method (FEM) to study dynamic fragmentation in ceramics [14, 15, 16]. Specifically, H. D. Espinosa et al. and G. Geraci et al. conducted studies modeling the dynamic fragmentation of polycrystalline bulk materials due to thermal stress-induced microcracking using Cohesive Zone Modeling (CZM) [14, 15, 16]. While CZM models effectively monitored inter- and trans-granular crack nucleation and propagation under thermomechanical conditions, they struggled with multiple crack growth or branching and presented challenges in positioning cohesive elements across complex microstructures [14, 15, 16].

In addition, an alternative method to the classical FEM is the Boundary Element Method (BEM). BEM has gained popularity due to its ability to discretize problems in terms of boundary variables, thereby reducing problem size [17]. Various studies have employed BEM in combination with CZM models to investigate brittle crack propagation [18, 19, 20] and thermally induced microcrack evolution under mechanical and thermomechanical loading conditions [15, 16, 21]. Despite its applicability in numerous studies, BEM has inherent limitations. A primary limitation is the necessity of accurately defining boundary conditions, as the method relies on the discretization of the problem domain’s boundary rather than the entire domain [15, 16, 18, 19, 20, 21]. Consequently, the accuracy of BEM results is highly dependent on the precision of the boundary conditions. This constraint restricts the application of BEM to complex and non-linear problems [15, 16, 18, 19, 20, 21].

Subsequently, Phase Field Modeling (PFM) emerged as an alternative to BEM and CZM. PFM has shown promise in addressing thermomechanical aspects observed in refractory materials, such as multiple crack nucleation, propagation and branching [22]. The PFM model has been successfully applied in various studies to investigate fracture initiation and propagation [22], solve thermo-fracture mechanical contact problems [23, 24] and examine the influence of anisotropic thermal properties [23, 25] and grain size in polycrystalline bulk materials [23]. However, while PFM is effective for studying brittle fracture growth under thermomechanical loading, it has notable shortcomings. Specifically, it is unsuitable for analyzing material failure under compressive loads due to unrealistic crack growth, an inability to model crack closure and difficulties in accounting for internal friction between crack surfaces (crack lips) [22, 23, 24].

Finally, the Discrete Element Method (DEM) emerged as an alternative technique to PFM, offering the capability to study failures—including multiple crack nucleation and propagation—under both compressive and tensile loading conditions, as well as crack closure mechanisms and frictional movements [26, 27]. Initially, DEM was employed for modeling the dynamic behavior of granular media [28, 29] and was later adapted for studying the fracture behavior of cohesive bulk media [30].

In the literature, numerous studies have utilized the so-called Bonded Particle Element Method (BPEM) with spherical discrete elements to study fracture of brittle media. Examples include flat-joint [31], cohesive beam [32, 33] or polycrystalline DEM [34] bond

models. These studies focused on the mechanisms of crack initiation and propagation at the microstructural scale. In BPEM, a cohesive medium is discretized using spherical discrete elements and microscale interactions are represented through input micro-properties of the bond models [30]. The apparent response of the entire discrete lattice structure is treated as the captured output property [31, 35]. Consequently, correlating the input micro-properties with the output apparent properties requires calibration techniques that are often labor-intensive and complex [32].

To address the need for a continuum-equivalent representation and eliminate the cumbersome calibration steps in BPEM, Andre et al. [36] proposed an advanced bond model [36], which can also be interpreted as a contact model. This model is based on the Distinct Lattice Spring Model (DLSM), originally developed by Zhao et al. for elasticity and brittle dynamic failure problems [37].

The main advantage of using lattice spring models instead of classical DEM (or BPEM) is to avoid tedious calibration processes of contact laws thanks to the usage of well-established mathematical relationships between bond lattice rheological parameters (such as stiffnesses) and material mechanical properties. However, the classical lattice spring models exhibit limitations concerning the Poisson's effect, as this effect depends on the lattice structure (e.g., coordination number) and not on the lattice rheological parameters. In such a way, only a fixed Poisson's ratio can be solved by classical lattice spring models.

DLSM proposes to overcome this limitation for a set of ordered or disordered particle lattices by computing Cauchy strain tensors based on the displacements of neighboring particles using a least squares method. This enables the direct usage of continuum mechanics stress/strain constitutive laws, without limitations concerning Poisson's effect. Indeed, this model introduces a non-local averaging computation for strain tensor deduction, which can lead to numerical instabilities, especially for high Poisson's ratios. Such instabilities can be mitigated by introducing numerical damping using decentered schemes in the temporal explicit integration. Therefore, this model is not well adapted for studies where dynamic effects play a major role, such as fragmentation due to high-velocity impacts.

Later, Zhao et al. proposed a four-dimensional lattice spring model [38] that overcomes this limitation and opens the usage of lattice models to dynamic studies [39]. Additionally, the four-dimensional lattice spring model was recently extended to tackle plastic fracture of metals [40].

The proposed study will focus particularly on microcracks occurring at the microstructure scale (e.g., typically the scale of grains and their neighbors). The assumption is made that the observed macroscopic nonlinear response (see Figure 2) is the consequence of the accumulation of a micro-crack network combined with internal thermal stresses due to thermal history. Therefore, no plasticity will be considered in this study. The micro-crack nucleation and propagation in aluminum titanate can be considered as mainly brittle for temperatures far from the melting point, due to its oxide ceramic nature that prevents dislocation motion, thus preventing plasticity [41]. Furthermore, since the cooling process is very slow (on the order of hours), dynamic effects can be neglected. For this reason, the iDLSM model proposed by André et al. [36] will be used in this study.

Herefore, this study adopts the DEM approach with the DLSM model, which remains relatively unexplored. This novel approach aims to bridge the computational gap in modeling anisotropic thermal expansion, studying the evolution of microcracks and understanding their influence on the material's thermomechanical properties and microstructural relationships. To achieve the objectives of this study, several enhancements to the original DLSM method [36] were necessary. These improvements include modeling anisotropic thermal expansion, incorporating periodic boundary conditions to address multiscale analysis and implementing crack-closure mechanisms with friction.

These advancements constitute a significant extension of the original method [36], enabling the investigation of novel problems that are challenging to address using conventional numerical methods based on continuum mechanics, such as FEM.

Finally, this new model facilitates the tracking of complex microcrack networks resulting from CTE mismatch, enhancing the understanding of their impact on apparent thermomechanical properties through thermomechanical DLSM simulations. This study focuses on Aluminum Titanate (AT) material, with experimental data taken from the study [2]. It is important to note that the reference AT material closely corresponds to the *Very Flexible* (VF) material described in the study [3]. Moreover, these simulations are conducted under the assumption that the phases in the model are chemically inert and don't undergo any phase transformation. Additionally, the silica interphases are not explicitly considered in the model, and the AT crystals are assumed to be mechanically isotropic. These two simplifying assumptions allow for the development of a simplified model of the AT material, which provides reasonably well-adjusted results in comparison with experimental

observations.

To demonstrate the application of this novel tool, the first section briefly introduces the DLISM. For more information about DLISM models and related numerical algorithms, readers can refer to [36, 42]. The subsequent sections outline new features that are not yet documented in the literature. Specifically, the second section focuses on the description of the Periodic Boundary Condition (PBC) in the DLISM context. The third section details the anisotropic thermal expansion modeling using DLISM. The fifth section introduces the polycrystalline numerical sample, while the sixth section presents a new strategy for crack management. The seventh section provides an overview of the various steps involved in thermomechanical simulations and the final section is dedicated to a discussion and conclusions derived from the simulation results.

2. Overview of the Distinct Lattice Spring Model

One of the greatest challenges within the DEM community has been to represent Discrete Element (DE) interactions in a manner equivalent to the continuum approach used in FEM. Drawing insights from various studies [37, 43, 44, 45], Andre et al. proposed an improved DLISM interaction model [36], referred to as iDLISM [36, 42], to create a numerical discrete lattice equivalent to a continuum medium. As described in the introduction, the iDLISM model can be classified as a BPEM-based approach within the Discrete Element Method framework, specifically designed to simulate the mechanics of continuum cohesive bulk media. Unlike standard BPEM methods that utilize spherical discrete elements, iDLISM employs polyhedral discrete elements to generate a domain that is continuum-equivalent. This process is achieved through Voronoi tessellation.

An overview of the main steps involved in sample generation is illustrated in two dimensions in Figure 3 (the two-dimensional views are provided as pedagogical illustrations only). To generate scattered points (also known as germs) for the tessellation, transitory spherical discrete elements (within a predefined size range) are packed into a bounding domain, as shown in Figure 3a. The packing process is achieved using the Cooker algorithm, which is implemented in the free discrete element software GranOO [46]. The centroids of these spherical DEs are then used as input germs for a Voronoi tessellation, producing polyhedral elements (Figure 3b) that perfectly fill the boundary volume without voids. Finally, the polyhedral DEs are interconnected using contacts/bonds (represented as white lines

in Figure 3c), which are generated through a Delaunay tessellation. The Delaunay triangulation identifies pairs of polyhedral discrete elements that share a common contact facet, allowing for the creation of bonds linking the centroids of the two polyhedral elements. For more detailed information about the procedure for generating polyhedral DEs and the libraries used for tessellations to create iDLISM domains, please refer to [36, 42].

Figure 3: Illustration of iDLISM model generation

Therefore, iDLISM stands out among the BPEM-based DEM approaches due to a crucial difference in the computation of reaction forces between discrete elements [42]. In standard BPEM approaches, reaction forces are directly calculated from the relative displacements of the two bonded discrete elements. In contrast, the iDLISM approach computes forces based on the strains derived from the two bonded discrete elements as well as contributions from their direct neighboring discrete elements [36, 42]. A brief overview of the key steps used to compute the reaction forces is illustrated using the 2D schematic sketch in Figure 4. Consider a polyhedral DE i in contact with n DEs $j_1, j_2, j_3, \dots, j_n$ via the contact surface represented by S_{ijk} (where $k = 1, 2, \dots, n$). The points O_i and O_{j_k} denote the geometrical centroids of the polyhedral DEs i and j_k . In the proposed iDLISM, the reaction forces of the bonds ij_k are deduced following the seven steps described below.

1. A continuum displacement field $\vec{d}_i(x, y, z)$ is computed for each discrete element (i) by considering the displacements of its neighboring elements. Here, Voigt's hypothesis is applied, assuming a linear displacement field between the central discrete element i and its n surrounding neighbors ($j_1, j_2,$

Figure 4: Illustration of a basic iDLSM problem in 2D

\dots, j_n). This assumption results in three vectorial unknowns for determining the local displacement field. Since the system of equations is generally overdetermined, the iDLSM employs the least squares method to estimate $\vec{d}_i(x, y, z)$.

2. By applying the gradient operator to $\vec{d}_i(x, y, z)$, a Cauchy strain tensor $\bar{\bar{\epsilon}}_i$ is computed for each discrete element. Voigt's hypothesis (linear displacement field) results in a constant strain tensor $\bar{\bar{\epsilon}}_i$, which is expressed at the centroid O_i of element (i) .
3. By averaging the strain tensors of the two bonded discrete elements i and j , a strain tensor $\bar{\bar{\epsilon}}_{ij}$ is calculated for each ij bond using the formula: $\bar{\bar{\epsilon}}_{ij} = \frac{1}{2}(\bar{\bar{\epsilon}}_i + \bar{\bar{\epsilon}}_j)$.
4. The first diagonal strain component, oriented along the ij bond direction, is directly determined from the relative displacements of the i and j discrete elements. Since this direct measure requires less averaging, one of the six $\bar{\bar{\epsilon}}_{ij}$ components is overwritten with this strain value. Additionally, a direct contribution of the relative displacements perpendicular to the ij bond direction is incorporated into the off-diagonal (shear) components of $\bar{\bar{\epsilon}}_{ij}$.
5. A Cauchy stress tensor $\bar{\bar{\sigma}}_{ij}$ is computed for each bond from $\bar{\bar{\epsilon}}_{ij}$ by applying a constitutive stress-strain law suitable for solid continuum media. Here, the Hooke's law for isotropic elastic media is used.
6. Using the direction \vec{n}_{ij} of the ij bond, the stress vector is computed as: $\vec{\Sigma}_{ij} = \bar{\bar{\sigma}}_{ij} \cdot \vec{n}_{ij}$.

7. Given the contact surface S_{ij} between discrete elements i and j , the reaction force \vec{f}_{ij} is computed as: $\vec{f}_{ij} = S_{ij} \cdot \vec{\Sigma}_{ij}$.

The primary advantage of discrete-based approaches such as DEM, compared to continuum-based methods like FEM, is their ability to manage discontinuities such as cracks. In this study, a simple local criterion is proposed for modeling brittle fracture [36]. The proposed criterion assumes that crack nucleation occurs only in mode I. This assumption is particularly relevant for brittle media, which are the focus of this study. In this model, if the cohesive normal bond stress $\sigma_{xx_{ij}}$, where the local axis x_{ij} for bond ij is normal to the S_{ij} contact surface (see Figure 4), reaches the failure strength σ_{max} , the bond is considered broken and is removed from the computation. The cohesive normal contact stress is computed as: $\sigma_{xx_{ij}} = \vec{\Sigma}_{ij} \cdot \vec{x}_{ij}$. When a bond reaches this threshold, the corresponding contact surface S_{ij} is identified as a *crack facet* (see Figure 5). Once designated as a crack facet, the surface loses its ability to transfer stresses and forces across it. In this model, the crack closure mechanism is not considered, as the bond definitively vanishes when it reaches the crack criterion. Since the targeted study focuses on thermal contraction, where crack closure remains an important and non-negligible mechanism, this phenomenon is introduced in a revised version of the crack model, as described in Section 6.

Figure 5: Crack-facet representation in iDLSM numerical sample

Therefore, common material mechanical properties, such as Young's modulus (E) and Poisson's ratio (ν), which are typically used in standard constitutive mechanical (stress-strain) laws, can be directly incorporated into the model. This integration eliminates the tedious calibration steps often required in BPDM and enhances the ability to adopt continuum mechanical principles [26]. For further details about this method, readers are encouraged to consult references [36, 42].

3. Periodic Boundary Condition

Periodic Boundary Conditions (PBC) is a widely recognized homogenization modeling technique first introduced by Papanicolau and Bensoussan [47] in the 1970s. Homogenization is a numerical technique that facilitates multiscale analyses, linking the micro- and macroscale by leveraging the periodicity of the microstructure [47, 48]. Additionally, researchers have promoted this technique to perform multiscale analysis in conjunction with various numerical approaches, including FEM [49], molecular dynamics [50] and DEM [28]. Furthermore, studies have highlighted that incorporating PBC helps eliminate free boundary surfaces by generating an infinite cohesive medium using a finite periodic cell. Given these benefits, the present study employs the PBC technique to model polycrystalline microstructures. Notably, embedding PBC within iDLSM modeling is a novel approach and remains undocumented in existing literature. Therefore, the numerical strategy used to implement PBC in the iDLSM context will be detailed in this section.

The strategy for generating a periodic iDLSM domain is illustrated using 2D schematic diagrams and 3D snapshots, as shown in Figure 6. Similar to the approach used for Free Boundary Condition (FBC) described in the previous section (see Figure 3), the construction of the numerical domain begins with the packing of spherical discrete elements using the Cooker algorithm [46]. The key difference lies in the replication of the central unit cell into 8 periodic cells in 2D, as illustrated in Figure 6a, to ensure periodicity. In 3D, this replication involves 26 periodic cells to achieve the same periodic boundary condition.

As the next step, the scattered centroids of the spherical DE (Figures 6a and 6b), including those located in the periodic cells, are used as germs to perform a Voronoi tessellation, generating a polyhedral DE domain (Figures 6c and 6d). The Voronoi tessellation follows the same strategy described in the previous section. Using germs located in the periodic cells ensures the periodicity of the polyhedral DEM domain. Once again, polyhedral DEs are connected using bonds generated through Delaunay tessellations (Figures 6e and 6f). Finally, to save computational time and memory during further simulations, unnecessary elements that do not interact with elements located in the central unit cell are removed from the domain (Figures 6g and 6h).

To validate this strategy, uniaxial tensile tests along the \vec{X} direction is presented in this section for preliminary understanding. Details about the computational methods for applying uniaxial mechanical loading in a

Figure 6: Procedure to generate PBC-DLSM box from initial spherical domain to polyhedral bonded domain without “useless” periodic elements

PBC-iDLSM context is given in Appendix A. Please note that the term “apparent” in this article always refers to the (homogenized) measurement of a physical quantity over the entire central cell. This should not be confused with local measurements at the discrete element

scale. An apparent quantity q will be denoted with angle brackets, $\langle q \rangle$.

To illustrate and validate this strategy, a hypothetical elastic material, as defined in Table 1, is mechanically loaded to perform a quasi-static uniaxial tensile test. For this purpose, a PBC-iDLSM numerical sample comprising 20,000 discrete elements within the central unit cell is used. This study aims to verify the accuracy of the deduced apparent mechanical properties, such as Young's modulus $\langle E \rangle$ and Poisson's ratio $\langle \nu \rangle$, by comparing them with the input mechanical properties E and ν provided in Table 1. The numerical sample is subjected to an imposed strain rate of 10^{-7} per iteration over a total of 10,000 iterations.

To minimize dynamic effects and expedite convergence toward the static solution, two different damping factors are combined. The first is a numerical damping factor, denoted as φ , which is introduced into the velocity Verlet integration scheme [36]. In this study, a value of $\varphi = 1.3$ is used. The second damping factor is a physical damping factor, denoted as γ , which is introduced into the iDLSM bond. This factor corresponds to a fraction of the critical damping coefficient [51]. A value of $\gamma = 0.4$ is used in this study.

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Unit
Young's modulus	E	20	GPa
Poisson's ratio	ν	0.2	-
Tensile strength	σ_{\max}	15	MPa
Number of DE	N_{DE}	20k	-

Table 1: Hypothetical material properties for elastic tensile test

Figure 7 summarizes the results of the quasi-static uniaxial tensile test. As expected, the targeted apparent stress state $\langle \bar{\sigma} \rangle$, described by equation A.3, is maintained in the numerical sample. The apparent Young's modulus $\langle E \rangle$ is deduced by taking the ratio of the measured apparent normal stress $\langle \sigma_{XX} \rangle$ along the loading direction \vec{X} to the imposed strain $\langle \varepsilon_{XX} \rangle$ along the same direction. It can be observed that the deduced apparent Young's modulus $\langle E \rangle$ converges to the input material Young's modulus E . Similarly, the apparent Poisson's ratios $\langle \nu_{YY} \rangle$ and $\langle \nu_{ZZ} \rangle$ along the \vec{Y} and \vec{Z} directions are deduced by monitoring the apparent strain contractions $\langle \varepsilon_{YY} \rangle$ and $\langle \varepsilon_{ZZ} \rangle$ in the respective directions. Like $\langle E \rangle$, the deduced $\langle \varepsilon_{YY} \rangle$ and $\langle \varepsilon_{ZZ} \rangle$ converge to the input material Poisson's ratio ν .

To validate the brittle failure behavior of the hypothetical material, a local tensile strength σ_{\max} is also introduced. As expected, the numerical sample exhibits a brittle failure which is shown on Figure 7 by a sud-

den decrease of the apparent stress $\langle \sigma_{XX} \rangle$ at 15 MPa which corresponds to the local failure value σ_{\max} . To enhance reader understanding and facilitate visualization, the sample snippet visible on Figure 7 is presented only for the central periodic cell where the cracks are highlighted in blue-green.

Figure 7: Evolution of stresses and Poisson's ratio versus strain for a PBC-iDLSM tensile test

In conclusion, the current study successfully demonstrated a strategy to impose mechanical loading on the iDLSM-PBC numerical sample, as illustrated by tensile tests on an elastic brittle hypothetical material. The results, presented in Figure 7, show both qualitatively and quantitatively good agreement with the expected behaviors and tendencies.

4. Anisotropic Thermal Expansion

Thermal expansion is a well-known material behavior characterized by a coefficient of expansion or contraction versus temperature change. As mentioned in the introduction, this study focuses on anisotropic thermal expansion, which is defined by the following thermal expansion coefficient tensor:

$$\bar{\bar{\alpha}} = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_x & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \alpha_y & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \alpha_z \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where α_x , α_y and α_z denote the coefficients of thermal expansion along the respective spatial axes. Pre-

viously, Andre et al. demonstrated a strategy for modeling isotropic thermal expansion using the DEM cohesive beam bond approach [30]. A similar strategy is adopted and adapted here to model anisotropic thermal expansion using iDLSM model. It is important to note that the proposed model can be applied to all contact and bond models based on the DEM-BPEM technique.

4.1. DEM formulation

Until now, modeling anisotropic thermal expansion within DEM has not been described in the literature. Consequently, this feature can be considered novel and the numerical background will be described in detail below. To explain the computation of thermal expansion, a pair of polyhedral elements is illustrated in Figure 8 in two dimensions. In this figure, points O_i and O_j represent the centroids of two bonded discrete elements. The model is assumed to have an initial temperature of T_0 and is in a relaxed state (no internal stress). The initial relaxed length vector of the bond at this temperature is l_x along \vec{x} and l_y along \vec{y} .

Figure 8: Sketch of anisotropic CTE management

In the current study, thermal expansion is applied by changing the bond relaxed lengths due to a temperature change $\Delta T = T - T_0$, similar to the isotropic case described in [30]. Consequently, when a temperature change ΔT is applied, the model is expected to expand. Considering discrete element (i) as the reference, discrete element (j) moves by Δl_x along \vec{x} and Δl_y along \vec{y} relative to discrete element (i). The new relative position of (j)'s centroid becomes O'_j . The displacements Δl_x and Δl_y (and Δl_z for 3D cases) are computed as:

$$\Delta l_x = \Delta T l_x \alpha_x \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta l_y = \Delta T l_y \alpha_y \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta l_z = \Delta T l_z \alpha_z \quad (4)$$

Now, considering the discrete element (i) as displacement-free, the displacements Δl_x and Δl_y (and

Δl_z for 3D) are equally distributed between the discrete elements (i) and (j). Additionally, the local bond axis \vec{x}_{ij} must be updated to account for angle changes caused by the anisotropic nature of the expansion. To save computational time, the shape and length of the discrete elements are not updated. In this case, the bond model is expressed in terms of engineering stresses rather than true stresses, which is a reasonable assumption given the low values of thermal strains.

Finally, it is important to note that this computation must be performed starting from the initial relaxed configuration at T_0 . Consequently, a thermomechanical computation involves two calculation steps: the first step computes the thermal expansion and the second step performs the mechanical computation, incorporating the previously computed thermal expansion. In the current study, a simplified approach is assumed by neglecting thermal conduction and considering a uniform temperature distribution across the sample. As a result, a separate thermal time step for thermal conduction distinct from the mechanical time step is not needed.

4.2. PBC-iDLSM Modelling

The previous Section 4.1 described the strategy for computing anisotropic thermal expansions for any DEM-PBM model, including PBC-iDLSM. Similarly, as discussed in Appendix A regarding imposing mechanical loading in a PBC context, thermal loading must also be adapted for PBC without free boundaries. In this study, thermal conduction is not considered and the temperature is assumed to be homogeneous throughout the numerical sample. Under this configuration, the entire sample is considered to be apparently stress-free. Consequently, the apparent targeted stress tensor should be:

$$\langle \bar{\sigma} \rangle = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

Again, the apparent strains $\langle \varepsilon_{xx} \rangle$, $\langle \varepsilon_{yy} \rangle$ and $\langle \varepsilon_{zz} \rangle$ must be computed to ensure the above stress-free state. The same *servo-control-loop* process described in Appendix A will be utilized to target the stress-free state defined by equation 5.

To validate this approach, a preliminary study involving a hypothetical elastic material with anisotropic thermal expansion coefficients is conducted. The material parameters used in this study are summarized in Table 2.

The thermal loading involves cooling the sample from 1200°C to 0°C (where 0°C is the targeted temperature) at a constant cooling rate of 0.05°C per iteration. The cooling process is followed by a dwell period

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Unit
Young's modulus	E	20	GPa
Poisson's ratio	ν	0.2	-
CTE along \vec{x}	α_x	-10	10^{-6} K^{-1}
CTE along \vec{y}	α_y	10	10^{-6} K^{-1}
CTE along \vec{z}	α_z	0	10^{-6} K^{-1}
Number of DE	N_{DE}	20k	-

Table 2: Hypothetical material properties for thermal test

lasting 12,000 iterations. The total number of iterations is 36,000, including both the cooling and dwell periods. To smooth the thermal loading, a hyperbolic tangent function is applied at the beginning and end of the cooling process. For this analysis, a PBC-iDLSM numerical sample consisting of 20,000 discrete elements is used.

From a material science perspective, the PBC-iDLSM model in this configuration can be considered as a monocrystal or single crystal. This study aims to investigate the accuracy of the apparent coefficients of thermal expansion relative to the given local coefficients of thermal expansion used as input parameters. Therefore, it is expected that the deduced apparent coefficients of thermal expansion $\langle\alpha_x\rangle$, $\langle\alpha_y\rangle$ and $\langle\alpha_z\rangle$ will converge to the local coefficients of thermal expansion in their respective directions.

The main results are summarized in Figure 9, which illustrates the evolution of the apparent thermal strain during the cooling process, beginning at 1200°C. As anticipated, the apparent thermal strain varies across individual directions, demonstrating the anisotropic behavior of the numerical sample. The apparent coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) in each direction can be calculated as the ratio of the apparent strains $\langle\epsilon_{xx}\rangle$, $\langle\epsilon_{yy}\rangle$ and $\langle\epsilon_{zz}\rangle$ in that direction to the temperature change ΔT . It is important to note that the initial relaxed state of the numerical sample, at 1200°C, is used as the reference state for calculating the apparent CTE. Thus, the apparent coefficients of thermal expansion in the three directions, \vec{X} , \vec{Y} and \vec{Z} , can be determined using the following expressions:

$$\langle\alpha_x\rangle = \frac{\langle\epsilon_{xx}\rangle}{\Delta T} \quad \langle\alpha_y\rangle = \frac{\langle\epsilon_{yy}\rangle}{\Delta T} \quad \langle\alpha_z\rangle = \frac{\langle\epsilon_{zz}\rangle}{\Delta T} \quad (6)$$

By taking the slopes of the three curves (see Figure 9), the apparent coefficient of thermal expansion converges to the material's (input) coefficient of thermal expansion for the numerical sample, as expected.

As demonstrated, the proposed model can mimic the anisotropic thermal expansion of a hypothetical homogeneous material using the PBC-iDLSM numerical

Figure 9: Evolution of strain versus temperature for a PBC-iDLSM cooling test

sample. From a materials science perspective, this hypothetical homogeneous material can be viewed as a monocrystalline material. The aim of this study is now to apply a similar numerical strategy to polycrystalline materials. Therefore, the next section is dedicated to introducing the numerical methods to (i) generate a polycrystalline numerical sample and (ii) discuss the ability of the numerical sample to describe the anisotropic behavior of the polycrystalline material.

5. Polycrystalline model

The aim of this study is to mimic the anisotropic thermal expansion of polycrystalline materials. In reality, polycrystalline materials have characteristic features such as grains, grain boundaries and local crystallographic orientations for each grain at the microstructural scale. Therefore, this section is dedicated to introducing the strategy for generating a polycrystalline numerical sample and discussing the ability of the numerical sample to describe the anisotropic behavior of polycrystalline materials.

5.1. Generation of polycrystalline domain

The strategy for generating the PBC-iDLSM numerical sample was discussed in Section 3. In this section, the strategy for adding grains, including their local orientations, will be described. Note that the term *crystal*

in this study is used as a synonym for the materials science term *grain*.

The strategy is illustrated in the schematic sketches in Figure 10. The first step involves generating a PBC-iDLSM model (see Figure 10a) with N_{DE} polyhedral discrete elements, following the same procedure described in Section 3. In this study, a polycrystalline material is defined as a material with N_{GR} grains, each having its own geometry, crystallographic orientation and touching neighboring grains. It is assumed that the grains exhibit random crystallographic orientations. To define the grain boundaries, a Voronoi tessellation is applied, with each Voronoi cell representing an individual grain, as shown in Figure 10b. This grain domain is then applied as a mask to the original PBC-iDLSM sample. Note that the grain domain must also be periodic to ensure the validity of the polycrystalline structure. The final step (see Figure 10c) involves applying the grain domain mask to the PBC-iDLSM sample to obtain the PBC-Periodic Grain Boundary (PBC-PGB) domain. In other words, the masking strategy identifies which grain boundary each of the DE centroids of the PBC-iDLSM belongs to. This results in a PGB-iDLSM sample with N_{GR} grains, where each grain is identified by unique colors and composed of a cluster of N_{GR}^{DE} discrete elements. A random crystallographic axis orientation is then assigned to each grain. Regarding the bonds, two situations may arise:

1. The two bonded discrete elements belong to the same grain. In this case, the bond is assigned to that grain.
2. The two bonded discrete elements belong to different grains. In this case, the bond is randomly assigned to one of the two grains. The same assignment should be used for all related periodic bonds to ensure the validity of the PBC.

The same methodology is applied to the 3D model, resulting in a 3D PGB-iDLSM model as shown in Figure 10d.

5.2. Anisotropic thermal expansion of polycrystalline domain

The previous section discussed the strategy for generating the PGB-iDLSM model. This section will implement the thermal anisotropy of each individual grain according to their crystallographic orientations, which were randomly assigned. Here, the central unit cell is $100 \times 100 \times 100 \mu\text{m}^3$ (see Figure 10d) to model the bulk cohesive medium. The strategy for implementing anisotropic thermal expansion was discussed in Section

Figure 10: Illustration of polycrystalline domain generation

4.2. The main difference here is the assignment of thermal expansion behavior depending on the local crystallographic orientation of the grains. To study the validity of the approach, similarly to Section 4.2, a cooling thermal load from 1200°C to 0°C is applied to the material parameters summarized in Table 3, which are related to the AT material at high temperature [2].

The following paragraph outlines the methodology for determining the values of the different thermo-mechanical parameters in Table 3. First, the assumption is made that AT grains are mechanically isotropic. The chosen Young's modulus value of 168 GPa corresponds to the experimental value measured at 1200°C (see Figure 17), where we consider the material to be free of defects [2]. As no clear measure of the AT Poisson's ratio at high temperature is available in the literature, the value of 0.28 was chosen from the Materials Project database [52]. Finally, the three CTE values were obtained from [53], which provide $\alpha_a = -2.38 \times 10^{-6} \text{K}^{-1}$, $\alpha_b = 11.97 \times 10^{-6} \text{K}^{-1}$, and $\alpha_c = 20.80 \times 10^{-6} \text{K}^{-1}$. The same decreasing ratio of 13% was applied to all these parameters to match the beginning of the experimental dilatometry measurements in Figure 15 at 1200°C . This ratio can be viewed as an implicit way of accounting for the silica interphase in the microstructure.

The temperature range [$1200^\circ\text{C} - 0^\circ\text{C}$] was chosen based on the experimental study [3], as AT exhibited significantly lower viscous behavior below 1200°C . It is assumed that crack healing mechanisms are present at temperatures higher than 1200°C . Furthermore, thermal internal stresses are considered to initiate at this temperature.

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Unit
Young's modulus	E	168	GPa
Poisson's ratio	ν	0.28	-
CTE along \vec{a}	α_a	-1.975	10^{-6} K^{-1}
CTE along \vec{b}	α_b	9.935	10^{-6} K^{-1}
CTE along \vec{c}	α_c	17.264	10^{-6} K^{-1}
Number of grains	N_{GR}	500	-
Number of DE	N_{DE}	20k	-

Table 3: Simulation parameters for AT material

Again, the apparent thermal expansion coefficients are monitored during the cooling simulations. Due to the presence of multiple grains, the apparent thermal expansion coefficient is expected to converge toward the mean value of the local thermal expansion coefficients of the individual grains. The apparent mean response of the polycrystalline numerical sample is shown in Figure 11. The mean value of the apparent coefficient of thermal expansion is obtained by averaging the apparent CTE values in the three directions:

$$\langle \alpha_{\text{mean}} \rangle = \frac{\langle \alpha_X \rangle + \langle \alpha_Y \rangle + \langle \alpha_Z \rangle}{3} \quad (7)$$

As expected, the apparent mean coefficient of thermal expansion, $\langle \alpha_{\text{mean}} \rangle$, converges toward a value of $8.415 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ (see Figure 11), which is very close to the mean value of the material's CTE (see Table 3), given by:

$$\alpha_{\text{mean}} = \frac{\alpha_a + \alpha_b + \alpha_c}{3} \approx 8.408 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1} \quad (8)$$

The polycrystalline numerical sample, while showing an apparent response similar to that of a single grain, requires additional statistical verification due to its randomized structure. The purpose of the statistical verification is to ensure that the chosen number of grains per central periodic cell and the number of discrete elements per grain are sufficient to make the apparent CTE response equivalent to the CTE behavior of single crystals. A statistical study is conducted using 9 different configurations of polycrystalline numerical samples. All 9 numerical samples are implemented with the same material parameters, as summarized in Table 3. The final results show that the mean CTE value for the nine samples is $8.410 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ with a very small standard deviation of $0.003 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$.

From the results of this statistical study, it can be seen that the average apparent mean coefficient of thermal expansion for all 9 numerical samples is very close to the mean of the local coefficient of thermal expansion

Figure 11: Evolution of mean CTE versus temperature for a PBC-PGB-iDLSM cooling test

(within 0.02%). Additionally, the standard deviation of the apparent mean coefficient of thermal expansion is very low, approximately 0.036%, which is almost negligible. This confirms that the results are reliable, given that there are 500 grains per central periodic cell and 40 discrete elements per grain.

In addition to this statistical study, the internal stress profile can also be monitored. For illustrative purposes, the stress profile of Sample 1 is tracked during the thermal treatment. Figure 12 shows the stress profiles of the numerical sample at two temperatures. During the cooling procedure, internal thermal stresses begin to appear due to the CTE mismatch across the grain boundaries and at the junctions where the grains meet or interact. The range of stress that are tracked on Figure 12 is between -375 MPa and $+375 \text{ MPa}$. Note that tensile stresses are considered positive, while compressive stresses are considered negative. In Figures 12a and 12b, the colored stress components correspond to the cohesive normal contact stress $\sigma_{xx_{ij}}$ of each bond (the same stress used for the failure criterion, as discussed in Section 2).

As shown in Figure 12a, no internal stress occurs at 1200°C , which corresponds to the start of the cooling simulation. However, at 300°C , which corresponds to a temperature variation of $\Delta T = -900^\circ\text{C}$, the stress becomes heterogeneous and a few bonds exhibit a stress state that can be considered critical, exceeding the ma-

material's failure strength. Therefore, crack management needs to be introduced to investigate fracture mechanisms during the cooling process across the polycrystalline numerical sample.

Figure 12: Snippets of stress state across polycrystalline numerical sample at two temperatures state

6. Crack opening and closing mechanism

In this study, we describe the crack nucleation and propagation process as it pertains to the iDLSM model, initially discussed in Section 2. To account for thermal stresses caused by anisotropic thermal expansion in AT materials, we introduce a failure strength that triggers crack nucleation when the local failure criteria, as defined in Section 2, are met. The crack opening mechanism follows a simplified scheme: once a bond exceeds its tensile strength σ_{\max} , it undergoes Mode I crack nucleation. The bond is then deactivated from the calculation, and the resulting crack facet does not transmit any internal forces.

The crack closure mechanism is introduced to the model to ensure force transmission when cracks begin to close. In this mechanism, normal compressive forces are transmitted across the crack facet, with frictional forces (if considered) contributing to stress transfer. However, in this study, we assume perfect sliding (friction coefficient = 0), so only normal forces are considered during crack closure, with no shear forces transmitted. As illustrated in Figure 13, the crack opening and closing scheme is implemented as follows: during the opening mode, the crack surfaces are separated by a small distance $\delta > 0$, and no tensile forces are transmitted. Once the crack surfaces come into contact ($\delta \leq 0$) during the closing mode, the bond regains its ability to transfer forces in the normal direction. This mechanism ensures stress and force transmission during crack closure.

To validate this post-crack mechanism, a cooling simulation is performed using the polycrystalline numeri-

Figure 13: 3D Illustration of the crack opening and closing

cal sample. The tensile strength value σ_{\max} of 375 MPa was selected to match the experimental value of Young's modulus at room temperature, which is approximately 20 GPa (see Figure 17). Thus, the material properties for this study are those listed in Table 3, with the added value of $\sigma_{\max} = 375$ MPa. The results of this model are shown in Figure 14, where crack facets are highlighted in blue. This numerical model will now be used to study the influence of crack nucleation and post-crack mechanisms on the evolution of the thermomechanical properties of the reference model material with respect to temperature.

Figure 14: Snippets of Polycrystalline numerical sample with complex microcracked network (crack opening and closing management) at 20°C

7. Thermomechanical simulation

This work focuses on replicating the behavior of refractory materials during the sintering process. Therefore, this section is dedicated to describing the various steps involved in the thermomechanical simulation and monitoring the evolution of the thermomechanical properties of the model material.

7.1. Reminder about the AT reference material

In this study, a polycrystalline Aluminium Titanate (AT) material has been chosen as the reference material (see Figure 1). It is of particular interest due to its very low negative CTE along the \vec{a} crystallographic axis and the relatively high CTE along the \vec{b} and \vec{c} axes

of its orthorhombic crystals at the microstructural scale [3]. The orthorhombic structure introduces significant anisotropic CTE between the crystallographic axes of the AT grains. This anisotropic CTE leads to high residual stresses across the grain boundaries during the cooling stage, from the sintering temperature to room temperature, due to CTE mismatch [3]. As explained in the introduction, these thermal stresses induce microcracks [3]. The presence of microcracks in the microstructure significantly influences physical macroscopic properties such as Young's modulus, CTE and others [3]. The evolution of CTE and Young's modulus with respect to temperature was explored by Mouiya et al. using experimental techniques in a recent study. The details of these experimental techniques are explained in reference [3]. These experimental results will be used as references for the proposed numerical study.

The aim of the present DEM model is to qualitatively compute the evolution of the apparent CTE and Young's modulus of the bulk sample during the cooling stage. The DEM numerical samples used here are similar to those presented in Section 5.2. As mentioned,, each grain in the numerical sample is assigned a random orientation, with each grain depicted in different colors in Figure 10d. Each grain is constructed by approximately assembling 40 discrete elements. The input data representing the local properties of each AT grain at 1200°C [3] are summarized in Table 3 combined with a tensile strength value σ_{\max} of 375 MPa .

7.2. Numerical results

The thermomechanical simulations described in this section consist of two steps:

1. A cooling simulation, representative of the cooling stage after sintering the material. In this step, cracks are allowed to initiate and propagate.
2. A pure mechanical tensile test, during which the cracks are not allowed to extend. These tests are performed on the cooled sample obtained from the previous step. The aim of this mechanical test is to extract the apparent Young's modulus of the microcracked numerical samples.

Additionally, the evolution of the CTE is monitored during the cooling simulations. At the initial stage, the numerical sample is assumed to be at 1200°C. The sample is assigned the input data summarized in Table 3 combined with a tensile strength value σ_{\max} of 375 MPa and it is assumed to be in a relaxed state at this high temperature. The temperature is considered homogeneous across the entire numerical sample. To perform

the cooling simulations, the numerical sample is subjected to thermal loading, from 1200°C to 20°C. As explained in Section 5.2, it is assumed that the sample begins to exhibit thermal stresses at this temperature. A cooling simulation (followed by a mechanical simulation) is performed for every 100°C of cooling.

During the cooling simulation, the apparent thermal strains $\langle \epsilon_{XX} \rangle$, $\langle \epsilon_{YY} \rangle$ and $\langle \epsilon_{ZZ} \rangle$ of the numerical sample are monitored and recorded. These strains are then averaged to deduce the apparent mean CTE, $\langle \alpha_{\text{mean}} \rangle$, following the equation:

$$\langle \epsilon_{\text{mean}} \rangle = \frac{\langle \epsilon_{XX} \rangle + \langle \epsilon_{YY} \rangle + \langle \epsilon_{ZZ} \rangle}{3} \quad (9)$$

in order to measure the average mean CTE $\langle \alpha_{\text{mean}} \rangle$.

By this process, the numerical dilatometry results for AT (apparent thermal strain vs temperature) are obtained, as shown in Figure 15 and compared to the experimental measurements. Figure 15 shows that the current numerical model can produce quantitative results for the AT material. Specifically, the model replicates the trend of contraction (decrease in thermal strain), which is consistent with the experimental results. On the other hand, around 700°C, the change in slope indicates a sudden increase in microcrack formation in the numerical sample.

This can also be observed in Figure 16, which shows the evolution of microcracks with respect to temperature. In Figure 16, the crack networks are depicted in different colors, indicating the presence of many isolated small crack networks. Additionally, it should be noted that the intrinsic properties of each grain (at the microstructural scale) remain unchanged at each temperature. Moreover, the apparent CTE of the numerical sample is influenced solely by the microcracking mechanism, as the input local CTE values remain constant throughout the cooling simulation.

After each cooling simulation from 1200°C to 20°C, the microcracked numerical samples undergo a quasi-static tensile test. During the tensile test, crack propagation is prevented, allowing the measurement of the Young's modulus of the microcracked samples. In this study, the apparent Young's modulus $\langle E \rangle$ is determined as the ratio of the apparent normal stress $\langle \sigma_{XX} \rangle$ to the imposed apparent strain $\langle \epsilon_{XX} \rangle$. The evolution of Young's modulus with respect to temperature is shown in Figure 17.

It is evident from Figure 17 that the Young's modulus decreases as the temperature drops from 1200°C. This indicates the promotion and evolution of the microcrack network in the numerical sample (Figure 16). Moreover,

Figure 15: Experimental and numerical dilatometry results of AT material

Figure 17: Experimental and numerical results of AT Young's modulus evolution versus temperature

Figure 16: Evolution of microcrack network

these quantitative results align with the trend observed in the experimental data.

8. Discussion and perspective

The proposed DEM model successfully mimics the complex material behavior observed at the macroscopic scale by implementing relatively simple thermomechanical physics at the microscopic scale. By accounting for microcracking induced by the coefficient of thermal expansion between grains, the model generates quan-

titative results regarding the macroscopic evolution of Young's modulus and thermal expansion during thermal treatment. Firstly, despite using simplified input material properties for the numerical samples compared to the real microstructure (see Figure 1), the results exhibited by the simulation align qualitatively and quantitatively with the experimental measurements. However, while the overall trend, including sudden changes in thermal expansion (Figure 15) and Young's modulus (Figure 17), is reasonably well reproduced using the DEM model, a notable difference remains in the suddenness of these changes. The main reason for this discrepancy could be the absence of large grains (which are present in the real microstructure, as shown in Figure 1). These large, elongated grains contribute to a higher density of microcracks within and around the surrounding grains. Additionally, the current numerical sample lacks discontinuities such as pores, which are present in the real microstructure. Also, the silica interphase was not taken into account explicitly. This may explain the small discrepancies between the model and the experimental data. Finally, this study focuses on the material experimentally characterized in [2], which corresponds to the 'Flexible' (F) material in the study by [3], highlighting the influence of grain size. Currently, the proposed model does not account for the influence of the grain size, but this represents an important direction for future development.

In addition, the numerical results obtained from the polycrystalline numerical samples can provide insights into the following perspectives:

- Monitoring local crack nucleation and propagation (under thermal and mechanical loading) across the numerical sample as a function of temperature;
- Monitoring the crack surface to identify isolated and merged cracks across the numerical sample;
- Identifying the nature of cracks (intragranular vs grain boundaries) based on their origin and location within the numerical sample;
- Monitoring the accumulation of irreversible strains during crack propagation in the tensile test and attempting to quantify the related energy consumption;
- Monitoring the distribution of cracks and strains across the numerical sample.

Therefore, with all these data, the influence of microcrack networks on the macroscopic thermomechanical response of the refractory material can be better understood. In addition, insights into the sustainability of the refractory material from a materials science perspective can be summarized.

9. Conclusion

In conclusion, the present DEM tool can depict the anisotropic thermal expansion and fracture behavior at the microstructure scale of polycrystalline material (due to CTE mismatch). Additionally, the model accounts for crack opening and closing, incorporating real physics to better understand the relationships between microstructure and macroscopic thermomechanical properties of refractory materials. For this purpose, Aluminum Titanate was used as the reference material to validate the numerical tool. The developed DEM tool and model successfully captured multiple microcrack networks formed during the cooling simulation, which is challenging to model using common mechanical engineering tools like FEM. The authors were able to monitor the thermomechanical properties of AT with respect to temperature during the thermomechanical simulation. This data provided insights into how microcracks (formed during the cooling stage) influence the thermomechanical macroscopic properties of AT. In the future, the DEM tool can be extended to investigate multiphase systems, such as systems containing AT aggregates, pores and an alumina matrix. The GranOO

platform adopted for this study should be upgraded for multiphase system analysis. This information could ultimately help the refractory industry improve their microstructure design.

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Appendix A. About mechanical loadings with PBC-IDLSM

In 3D PBC models, external mechanical loadings cannot be directly applied to the numerical sample due to the absence of boundary surfaces. Within the PBC context, external mechanical loading must be indirectly applied by stretching the central periodic cell. This process is illustrated with a 2D schematic diagram in Figure A.18. Stretching is applied by adjusting the lengths L_X , L_Y and L_Z of the central periodic cell along the global axes \vec{X} , \vec{Y} and \vec{Z} , respectively. The initial dimensions of the central periodic box are assumed to be L_{X_0} , L_{Y_0} and L_{Z_0} . For uniaxial loading, the apparent strain tensor $\langle \bar{\epsilon} \rangle$ is considered without deviatoric shear components and is expressed as:

$$\langle \bar{\epsilon} \rangle = \begin{bmatrix} \langle \epsilon_{XX} \rangle & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \langle \epsilon_{YY} \rangle & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \langle \epsilon_{ZZ} \rangle \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

with :

$$\langle \epsilon_{XX} \rangle = \frac{\Delta L_X}{L_{X_0}} \quad \langle \epsilon_{YY} \rangle = \frac{\Delta L_Y}{L_{Y_0}} \quad \langle \epsilon_{ZZ} \rangle = \frac{\Delta L_Z}{L_{Z_0}} \quad (\text{A.2})$$

In this context, ΔL_X , ΔL_Y and ΔL_Z represent the length variations of the central unit cell during simulations, while L_{X_0} , L_{Y_0} and L_{Z_0} denote the initial lengths of the central unit cell at the start of the simulations.

In the case of tensile loading along the \vec{X} axis, the $\langle \epsilon_{XX} \rangle$ component is directly controlled by the applied boundary condition, whereas the $\langle \epsilon_{YY} \rangle$ and $\langle \epsilon_{ZZ} \rangle$ components are free parameters determined by the computation. To compute the $\langle \epsilon_{YY} \rangle$ and $\langle \epsilon_{ZZ} \rangle$ strain components,

a customized *servo-control-loop* process is employed, which will be described in the following sections. For the uniaxial test, the objective is to determine the values of $\langle \epsilon_{YY} \rangle$ and $\langle \epsilon_{ZZ} \rangle$ that satisfy the following apparent stress state.

$$\langle \bar{\sigma} \rangle = \begin{bmatrix} \langle \sigma_{XX} \rangle & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

To target the desired stress state $\langle \bar{\sigma} \rangle$, the resultant apparent stress must be monitored throughout the simulation. Figure A.18 illustrates this monitoring process. It involves measuring the forces acting along the boundaries via the so-called boundary bonds (highlighted in bold lines in Figure A.18). These boundary bonds connect a central unit cell discrete element (DE) to a cloned DE belonging to a periodic cell. In the 2D case, the boundary bonds are marked as X^+ , X^- , Y^+ and Y^- , while for the 3D case, they include Z^+ and Z^- , as depicted in Figure A.18. The apparent stresses are determined by summing the components of the bond forces \vec{F}_{ijk} projected onto the normal of a given boundary k (k being X^+ , X^- , Y^+ , Y^- , Z^+ , or Z^-). This total is then divided by the corresponding surface area (S_{X^+} , S_{X^-} , S_{Y^+} , S_{Y^-} , S_{Z^+} , or S_{Z^-}) of the central unit cell.

Figure A.18: The central periodic unit cell with its boundaries in 2D

Therefore, the apparent stress tensor $\langle \bar{\sigma} \rangle$ is calculated based on the stresses acting on the X^+ , X^- , Y^+ , Y^- , Z^+ and Z^- boundaries using the following equations. Apparent shear stresses are neglected in this study.

$$\langle \bar{\sigma} \rangle = \begin{bmatrix} \langle \sigma_{XX} \rangle & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \langle \sigma_{YY} \rangle & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \langle \sigma_{ZZ} \rangle \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{A.4})$$

where :

$$\langle \sigma_{XX} \rangle = \frac{1}{2} (\langle \sigma_{XX}^{X^+} \rangle + \langle \sigma_{XX}^{X^-} \rangle) \quad (\text{A.5})$$

$$\langle \sigma_{YY} \rangle = \frac{1}{2} (\langle \sigma_{YY}^{Y^+} \rangle + \langle \sigma_{YY}^{Y^-} \rangle) \quad (\text{A.6})$$

$$\langle \sigma_{ZZ} \rangle = \frac{1}{2} (\langle \sigma_{ZZ}^{Z^+} \rangle + \langle \sigma_{ZZ}^{Z^-} \rangle) \quad (\text{A.7})$$

with:

$$\langle \sigma_{XX}^{X^+} \rangle = \frac{\vec{n}_{X^+}}{S^{X^+}} \sum \vec{f}_{ijX^+} \langle \sigma_{XX}^{X^-} \rangle = \frac{\vec{n}_{X^-}}{S^{X^-}} \sum \vec{f}_{ijX^-} \quad (\text{A.8})$$

$$\langle \sigma_{YY}^{Y^+} \rangle = \frac{\vec{n}_{Y^+}}{S^{Y^+}} \sum \vec{f}_{ijY^+} \langle \sigma_{YY}^{Y^-} \rangle = \frac{\vec{n}_{Y^-}}{S^{Y^-}} \sum \vec{f}_{ijY^-} \quad (\text{A.9})$$

$$\langle \sigma_{ZZ}^{Z^+} \rangle = \frac{\vec{n}_{Z^+}}{S^{Z^+}} \sum \vec{f}_{ijZ^+} \langle \sigma_{ZZ}^{Z^-} \rangle = \frac{\vec{n}_{Z^-}}{S^{Z^-}} \sum \vec{f}_{ijZ^-} \quad (\text{A.10})$$

In the previous equations, \vec{n}_{X^+} , \vec{n}_{X^-} , \vec{n}_{Y^+} , \vec{n}_{Y^-} , \vec{n}_{Z^+} and \vec{n}_{Z^-} are the unit normal vectors perpendicular to S^{X^+} , S^{X^-} , S^{Y^+} , S^{Y^-} , S^{Z^+} and S^{Z^-} , respectively. These represent the bounding rectangular surfaces of the parallelepiped central unit cell. The surface areas can be simply computed as:

$$S^{X^+} = L_Y \times L_Z \quad S^{X^-} = L_Y \times L_Z \quad (\text{A.11})$$

$$S^{Y^+} = L_X \times L_Z \quad S^{Y^-} = L_X \times L_Z \quad (\text{A.12})$$

$$S^{Z^+} = L_X \times L_Y \quad S^{Z^-} = L_X \times L_Y \quad (\text{A.13})$$

The resultant apparent stresses are computed as the mean of the two opposite stresses, as described in equations A.5, A.6 and A.7. Once the resultant apparent stress across the central periodic box is deduced, the corresponding resultant apparent strains are determined. The apparent strain along a given boundary (X^+ , X^- , Y^+ , Y^- , Z^+ , or Z^-) is calculated as the change in length divided by its initial length (see equation A.2). Shear components can also be deduced by monitoring the change in the angles of the boundary surfaces of the central periodic box relative to their initial state. However, this aspect will not be detailed, as apparent shear stresses are considered negligible for the mechanical loading conditions targeted in this study.

Thanks to these formulas, the apparent stresses and strains of the central unit cell can be computed during a simulation. However, if the targeted stress state is not yet achieved, a *servo-control-loop* numerical technique is employed to guide the simulation toward the desired

stress state. This technique monitors the difference between the current stress state of the central periodic box and the targeted stress state. Based on this difference, the simulation adjusts whether the length of the central unit cell should increase or decrease along the \vec{X} , \vec{Y} and \vec{Z} directions. The Proportional Integral Derivative (PID) controller is used to incrementally adjust the lengths of the central unit cell to achieve the targeted apparent stress state. To ensure numerical stability, the increment values are constrained within a predefined minimum and maximum threshold. The PID strategy minimizes the stress error $\langle \bar{\sigma}_{\text{error}} \rangle$ by adjusting the stretching of the central periodic cell according to the following equations:

$$\langle \bar{\sigma}_{\text{error}} \rangle = \langle \bar{\sigma} \rangle - \langle \bar{\sigma}_{\text{target}} \rangle \quad (\text{A.14})$$

where :

- $\langle \bar{\sigma} \rangle$ is the current apparent monitored stress state;
- $\langle \bar{\sigma}_{\text{target}} \rangle$ is the apparent targeted stress state.

Incremental stretches δL_X , δL_Y and δL_Z of the central periodic cell must be determined to minimize the stress error. The PID controller facilitates this process using the following equation:

$$\bar{\delta L} = K_p \langle \bar{\sigma}_{\text{error}} \rangle + K_i \int \langle \bar{\sigma}_{\text{error}} \rangle dt + K_d \frac{d\bar{\sigma}_{\text{error}}}{dt} \quad (\text{A.15})$$

where $\bar{\delta L}$ is the stretch matrix defined as :

$$\bar{\delta L} = \begin{bmatrix} \delta L_X & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \delta L_Y & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \delta L_Z \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{A.16})$$

and K_p , K_i and K_d represent the proportional gain, integral gain and derivative gain, respectively, while t denotes the simulated time. The integral mode corrects any offset that may arise between the targeted stress state and the current stress state. Lastly, the derivative mode anticipates the system's progression by analyzing the rate of change of the apparent stresses of the bonds with respect to time.

In this study, it is assumed that the stretch along a given direction is directly responsible for the stress variation in the same direction. This assumption is reasonable given the mechanical loading conditions targeted in this study.

The acceptable increment or decrement value for δL_X , δL_Y and δL_Z is constrained between $\pm 1\%$ of the initial lengths L_{X_0} , L_{Y_0} and L_{Z_0} . Note that δL_X , δL_Y and

δL_Z represent the length variations between two consecutive time steps. Furthermore, in the case of uniaxial stretching along the \vec{X} -direction, only the incremental elongations δL_Y and δL_Z are guided by the *servo-control-loop* technique.